

BENZIMIDAZOLE DERIVATIVES AS PROMISING BIOACTIVE AGENTS RECENT DEVELOPMENTS IN ANTIMICROBIAL, ANTIFUNGAL, AND ANTHELMINTIC RESEARCH

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ABSTRACT

benzimidazole constitutes a vital class of nitrogen-containing heterocyclic compounds that have drawn considerable interest in pharmaceutical research owing to their diverse biological potential. The structural combination of benzene and imidazole rings provides a stable core capable of strong interactions with a wide range of biological targets. Numerous investigations have highlighted the pronounced antimicrobial, antifungal, and anthelmintic properties of benzimidazole derivatives. Their biological activity arises mainly from the inhibition of key metabolic and enzymatic functions necessary for microbial and parasitic growth. Well-known therapeutic agents such as albendazole, mebendazole, and thiabendazole exemplify the clinical utility of this scaffold in managing parasitic and infectious diseases. Modifications at various positions of the benzimidazole nucleus have been shown to enhance potency, specificity, and pharmacokinetic behaviour. Therefore, the benzimidazole framework remains highly promising template

for the rational design of next-generation antimicrobial and antiparasitic drugs with improved efficacy and safety profiles.

KEYWORDS: Benzimidazole, Chemistry, Antimicrobial, Antifungal, and Anthelmintic activity.

INTRODUCTION

Benzimidazole & its derivatives form an important class of heterocyclic compounds that have gained significant attention in the field of medicinal and pharmaceutical chemistry. Their structural versatility & wide range of biological activities make them valuable scaffolds in drug discovery and development. Numerous studies have demonstrated that benzimidazole-based compounds possess broad spectrum of pharmacological activities, including antimicrobial, antiviral, antifungal, anti-inflammatory, antitumor, antiparasitic, and antiprotozoal properties. Due to these diverse bioactivities, the benzimidazole nucleus has been extensively explored as a core structure in designing novel therapeutic agents.^[1] Over the past several decades, continuous research efforts have identified benzimidazole as a privileged heterocyclic system present in many clinically useful drugs. Molecules containing this nucleus have shown significant pharmacological potential, such as anticonvulsant, antihypertensive, antihistaminic, analgesic, anticoagulant, anticancer, & proton pump inhibitory effects. Several marketed drugs are derived from this scaffold, including albendazole, mebendazole, and thiabendazole (anthelmintic agents. carbendazim (fungicidal agent) The wide therapeutic applicability of benzimidazole derivatives highlights their importance as potential leads for the synthesis of new pharmacologically active compounds.^[2]

Benzimidazole is a heterocyclic compound formed by the fusion of a benzene ring with an imidazole ring, making it a fundamental structure in heterocyclic chemistry. Its derivatives have attracted significant interest due to their diverse applications, particularly in pharmaceuticals, agriculture, & materials science. Of special note, the 5,6-dimethylbenzimidazole unit is an essential component of vitamin B12, highlighting the biological importance of this class of compounds.^[3] In chemical nomenclature, the 2-position of benzimidazole is sometimes referred to as the μ - position. Benzimidazoles with a hydrogen atom attached to the nitrogen at the 1-position can readily undergo tautomerization, which affects chemical properties, biological activity.^[4]

Tautomerization Form

The first benzimidazole compound was prepared in 1872 by Hoebrecker, who synthesized 2,5- (or 2,6-) dimethylbenzimidazole. This early discovery paved the way for extensive research into the chemistry, synthesis, and applications of benzimidazole derivatives.^[3]

Chemistry

Benzimidazoles prepared from the reaction of o-phenylene diamines was treated with acetic acid. The mixture was heated in water bath at 100°C for 15-18hrs. After cooling, 10% sodium hydroxide solution was added slowly with thorough mixing by rotation of the flask until the mixture was just alkaline to litmus. The crude Benzimidazole was collected with suction in a Buchner funnel. Ice cold water is used to rinse all solid out of the reaction flask. The crude precipitate is washed with cold water and then recrystallized with water.^[5]

Biological Activity of Benzimidazole

In the following sections, the recent developments in benzimidazole derivatives their broad spectrum of pharmacological activities are discussed.

Antimicrobial Activity

Antimicrobial agents are a special class of compounds capable even in high dilutions of destroying or inhibiting microorganisms is known as antimicrobial agents. Mechanism of action of antimicrobial drugs may be bactericidal or bacteriostatic. Bactericidal drugs are very much useful in life- threatening situations, endocarditis, patients with low polymorph nuclear count and conditions in which bacteriostatic drugs do not cause a cure. Bacteriostatic drugs depend on the host defense mechanisms, such as phagocytes to kill the bacteria.^[6]

As per analysis every year 7, 00,000 people losing battle to anti-microbial resistant per year and another 10 million projected to die from it by 2050, AMR alone is killing more people than cancer & road traffic accidents combined together.^[7] Literature survey shows that among the benzimidazole derivatives, 2-substituted ones are found to be pharmacologically more potent hence. A series of 1,2-disubstituted-1H benzimidazole-N alkylated-5-carboxamide derivatives are very potent antibacterial activities against *S. aureus* and methicillin resistant *S. aureus*. Various Chloro & dichloro substituted benzimidazole also possess antibacterial activities.^[8] Their mechanism of action has been elucidated that the macrolides bind reversibly to the nucleotide A2058 in domain V of the 23S rRNA in the ribosomal 50S subunit and block protein synthesis. The predominant mechanism of resistance involves the

methylation of A2058 by a ribosomal methylase encoded by the *erm* gene, which confers a high level of resistance to macrolide- lincosamide streptograminB antibiotics. Third-generation macrolides known as ketolides such as telithromycin and cethromycin were developed to overcome *erm*- resistant bacteria through interacting with a secondary ribosomal binding site A752 directly in domain II of the 23S rRNA by their C-11-12 carbamate or C-6 side chains in addition to the main interaction of the drugs in domain.^[9] Microorganisms, whether present inside or outside the body, may cause disease due to the presence of some disease-causing elements in them. A lot of elements that empower effective penetration and harm of the host include poisons, contaminants, antigens and enzymes. Disease or illness caused by microorganisms can be counteracted, overseen and treated by using antimicrobial agents which are known as antibiotics. These compounds restrain the growth or destroy the microorganisms. Antibiotics are generally obtained from natural sources, but now they are synthesized in the labs. In recent years, medicinal chemists focused on the synthesis of novel drugs bearing heterocyclic moieties, because heterocyclic compounds possess a broader spectrum of therapeutic activities. Especially, nitrogen-containing heterocyclic moieties possess potential medicinal values like Quinine, Morphine, metronidazole etc. Furthermore, different nitrogen- containing heterocyclic compounds which are fused with other rings have been found to possess antimicrobial activities. So, the nitrogen-containing ring system seems, by all accounts, to be a standout amongst the most noticeable contender to investigate and assess their properties as antimicrobial agents. Among the N-heterocyclic rings Imidazole, benzimidazole, give off an impression of being the most attractive ones. Some benzimidazole derivatives when used with colistin show a synergistic effect against gram-negative bacteria. Schiff base of benzimidazole also possesses good antimicrobial activities.^[10]

Antifungal Activity

Fungi exist in two basic forms: yeasts and moulds. Yeasts are typically single, small, oval cells, whereas mould colonies consist of filamentous strands called hyphae. Some fungi are dimorphic, existing as either yeasts or moulds depending on the external environment. Some species, however, are adventitious pathogens in humans, causing superficial, subcutaneous or systemic infection. Most fungi causing systemic infection do so by direct inhalation into the lung or by invasion of a wound site. Others, such as *Candida albicans*, are commensal inhabitants of the gastrointestinal tract and skin, which under certain conditions may proliferate and migrate into the systemic circulation. Fungal infections can affect anyone and

they can appear on several part of the body.^[11] Fungal infections can be contagious. They can spread from one person to another. In some cases, you can also catch disease-causing fungi from infected animals or contaminated soil or surfaces.^[12] Infectious diseases have emerged as a major global health concern over recent decades, largely due to the rising resistance of microorganisms to existing antimicrobial agents. The prevalence of multidrug-resistant strains, particularly among Gram-positive bacteria and pathogenic fungi, has significantly limited the efficacy of current therapies. Among antifungal agents, fluconazole, a first-line triazole drug recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO), has shown remarkable efficacy against *Candida albicans* and *Cryptococcus neoformans*, owing to its potent activity, excellent safety profile, and favorable pharmacokinetics. However, it remains ineffective against invasive *Aspergillus* infections and lacks fungicidal properties. Furthermore, extensive clinical use has led to the emergence of fluconazole-resistant *Candida* isolates.^[13] To overcome these limitations, several researchers have synthesized and evaluated novel antifungal agents. developed spiro[indole-thiazolidinones] with activity against *Rhizoctonia solani*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, and *Colletotrichum* species. synthesized aryl-substituted bisbenzimidazolyl-5-carboxamidines exhibiting antifungal potential, while prepared 2-substituted benzimidazoles, tetrahydro benzimidazoles, and imidazoles with notable antibacterial and antifungal effects. Similarly, reported benzimidazole derivatives with significant antifungal activity, the latter emphasizing the role of lipophilicity against *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*.^[14]

Anthelmintics Activity

Soil-transmitted helminth treatment drugs are called anthelmintics. (STH) infections are caused by different species of parasitic worms. They are transmitted by eggs present in human feces, which contaminate the soil in areas where sanitation is very poor.^[15] The benzimidazoles have been developed as broad-spectrum anthelmintic agents. The most useful have modifications at the 2nd and 5th positions of the benzimidazole ring system. Thiabendazole, Mebendazole, and Albendazole have been used extensively for the treatment of human helminth infections. The benzimidazoles inhibit microtubule polymerization by binding to β -tubulin. The selective toxicity benzimidazoles bind parasite β -tubulin with much higher affinity than the mammalian protein. Drug resistance in nematodes may involve expression of a mutated β -tubulin. There is no evidence of emerging resistance among human nematodes.^[16] More than 1.5 billion people or 24% of the world's population are infected with soil-transmitted helminth infections worldwide.^[15] Over 267 million preschool-age

children and over 568 million school-age children live in areas where these parasites are intensively transmitted, and are in need of treatment and preventive interventions. Globally over 600 million people are estimated to be infected by *S. stercoralis* however, since also this parasite is transmitted in areas where sanitation is poor. Soil-transmitted helminths are transmitted by eggs that are passed in the faeces of infected people. Eggs are contaminated water sources by children who play in the soil and put their hands in mouths without washing them. The worms feed on host tissues, including blood, which leads to a loss of iron and protein and hookworms' addition cause chronic intestinal blood loss that can result in anaemia, intestinal manifestations (diarrhoea and abdominal pain), malnutrition, general malaise and weakness, and impaired growth and physical development. The WHO recommended medicine albendazole (400 mg) and mebendazole (500 mg) easy to administer by non-medical personnel.^[15] Soil-transmitted nematode infections can be prevented by avoidance of faecal soil contamination or skin contact (wearing shoes). Screening methods for anthelmintic drugs *Pheretimaposthuma*(Earthworm), *Ascaridiagalli*(Roundworm), *Raillietina spiralis* (Tapeworm).^[17]

Sr.no	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	X
6a	-	H	H	H	H	N
6b	H	H	COOH	H	H	C
6c	OH	H	SO ₃ H	H	H	C

[8]

[11]

11a	11b	11c	11d
-OCH ₃	OCH ₃	-OCH ₃	-OCH ₃
-CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	4-CH ₃ OC ₂ H ₄

[9]

[12]

Sr.no	R	R ₁
9	5,6-dichloro	p-fluorophenyl piperazine

Sr. no	R
12a	-Ph
12b	-o-OH-Ph
12c	-p-OH-Ph

[10]

Sr.no	R
10a	-NO ₂
10b	-Cl
10c	-OCH ₃
10d	-OH

[13]

Sr.no	R
13a	-Cl
13b	-Me

[16]

Sr.no	R
16a	-Cl
16b	-4-Morpholinyl

[14]

[17]

Sr.no	Ar
17a	
17b	

[15]

Sr.no	R1	R2
15a	H	CH3
15b	C6H5	CH3
15c	CH2=CH	CH3

Sr.no	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₄
18a	F	H	OH	OH
18b	Cl	H	OH	OH

Sr.no	R
21a	6-CH ₃
21b	7-CH ₃
21c	8-CH ₃

Sr.no	R
22a	CH ₃
22d	

Sr. no	(Benz)azole
20a	
20b	
20c	

Sr.no	R ₁	R ₂
23a	-CH ₃	p-OCH ₃
23b	-CH ₃	m-p-d(OCH ₃)
23c	-O ₂ H	p-Cl

Sr.no	R
27a	3-OH
27b	3-OCH ₃
27c	4-OH
27d	4-OCH ₃

Sr.no	R	R1
25	NO ₂	CH ₃

Sr.no	R
28a	-o-Cl
28b	-p-Cl

Sr.no	R
26a	Cl
26b	CH ₃

Fig. 1: Structures of some established benzimidazole derivatives as Antimicrobial, Antifungal, and Anthelmintic agents.

Conclusion and future aspects

The discussions above clearly demonstrate that the benzimidazole ring structure plays a crucial role in medicinal chemistry and remains an active focus of pharmaceutical research. As a vital pharmacophore in modern drug discovery, benzimidazole derivatives have shown remarkable therapeutic potential. Numerous studies have revealed that benzimidazole-based compounds possess broad pharmacological activities and have been successfully developed as anticancer, antibacterial, antifungal, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, anti-HIV, antioxidant, anticonvulsant, antitubercular, antidiabetic, antileishmanial, and antihistaminic agents. Many of these compounds are widely used due to their low toxicity, high bioavailability, good biocompatibility, and strong therapeutic efficacy. Given their diverse biological activities and multiple molecular targets, benzimidazole anticipated that further exploration of this core structure will lead to the design of novel molecules with improved biological properties, higher selectivity, and the development of innovative synthetic strategies.

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